

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF A 2080 Al/SiC COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue behavior of a 2080/SiC/30_p composite and 2080 Al alloy has been investigated for different matrix microstructures. A thermo-mechanical heat treatment has been utilized to achieve fine and homogeneously distributed spacing of S'-precipitates, resulting in high static and dynamic strengths. S'-precipitate spacing was identical in both base alloy and composite. Yield strengths for the composites were 555 MPa for the T8 heat treatment and 445 MPa for the T6 heat treatment, fatigue strengths at 10⁷ cycles are 210 MPa and 240 MPa, respectively. Explanations for the improved fatigue strength are related to differences in slip character and ductility due to different heat treatments.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic reinforced aluminum composites combine the low density of aluminum alloys with high static and cyclic strength levels [1-8]. They allow the tailoring of these and other properties such as coefficient of thermal expansion or modulus of elasticity. Particularly important for many applications is the improved fatigue strength which can be achieved by composites fabricated via powder metallurgical processing [3, 4, 8]. Although a number of investigations have shown improved fatigue lifetimes and endurance limits of composites compared to their unreinforced counterparts, the results are still inconclusive [4-10]. The understanding of the mechanisms by which reinforcements strengthen aluminum alloys is limited and still controversial. In part, this is due to the lack of systematic studies on microstructural effects and an inability to achieve identical microstructures in both the matrix of a composite and the corresponding base alloy.

The goal of the work presented here is to investigate the effects of SiC reinforcements on fatigue properties of a 2080 Al alloy for a variety of matrix microstructures while keeping the reinforcement parameters constant.

EXPERIMENTAL

A powder metallurgical 2080 Al alloy and a 2080/SiC/30_p composite were investigated in this study. Materials were supplied by Alcoa Technical Center. The composition of the base alloy and the matrix of the composite is Al13.58Mg1.86Cu0.25Zr. The composite contained 30 vol% SiC particles of nominal gradation F-600. The extruded materials were subjected to

T8 or T6 heat treatments. Both heat treatments consisted of solutionizing at 493°C for 2 hrs followed by artificially aging at 175°C for 24 hrs. For the T8 heat treatment, a cold rolling step of 5% reduction in thickness was inserted between solutionizing and ageing. To conduct an over-aging study, samples of the T8 heat treated material were further aged at 200, 225 or 250°C for 24 hrs.

SiC particle size and distribution were investigated by optical microscopy utilizing a digital image analyzer for quantitative analysis. Samples for transmission electron microscopy were electrolytically thinned in a solution of 20% nitric acid in methanol at -20°C and 15 V. Tensile tests were performed at an initial strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} . Stress controlled fatigue tests were conducted in axial push-pull mode with an R-ratio of -1 and a frequency of 30 Hz. A precision alignment fixture was utilized for mechanical tests to minimize bending. Fatigue specimens were machined using low-stress grinding.

RESULTS

MICROSTRUCTURE

Microstructural investigations revealed a macroscopically homogeneous microstructure for the 2080/SiC composite as shown in figure 1. Some banding was visible parallel to extrusion direction, resulting from areas of higher and lower particle density. The average SiC particle diameter in the composite was 10 μm . A small number of particles with diameters around 2 μm was observed, which were presumably broken during the compaction process.

Figure 1 Optical micrographs of 2080/SiC/30p, parallel (a) and normal (b) to direction of extrusion

TEM investigations revealed the presence of predominantly S' -precipitates, but differences in precipitation size and distribution were observed, as shown in figure 2. In T8 heat treatment, the S' -precipitates were extremely fine, uniformly distributed and of the same size and spacing in both the base alloy (Figure 2a) and the composite (Figure 2b). The T8 plus overaging heat treatment led to coarser, but evenly distributed S' -precipitates, as shown in figure 2e for the 250°C condition. Precipitate size increased from 28 nm for the T8 heat treatment to 48, 58 and 87 nm for the 200°C, 225°C and 250°C overaging heat treatments, respectively. In the T8 condition, the S' -precipitate spacing was the same in both the composite and the unreinforced base alloy.

Figure 2

TEM micrographs of 2080-T8 (a), 2080/SiC-T8 (b), 2080-T6 (c), 2080/SiC-T6 (d) and 2080/SiC-T8+250 (e)

TENSILE PROPERTIES

Strength levels and moduli of SiC containing composites were significantly higher than for their unreinforced counterparts, as summarized in table 1. The composite 2080/SiC-T8 showed a 0.2% yield strength of 545 MPa versus 490 MPa for the alloy 2080-T8. After T6 heat treatment, considerably lower yield strengths were observed with 445 MPa for the composite and 390 MPa for the base alloy. Less dramatic differences in UTS were observed: 600 MPa for 2080/SiC-T8 and 560 MPa for 2080/SiC-T6, 560 MPa for 2080-T8 and 520 MPa for 2080-T6. For the composites in the overaged conditions, yield strength levels decreased with increasing overaging temperature, down to 295 MPa for the 250°C treatment. Work hardening rates were taken at 0.5% plastic strain (Table 1). They were lower for the T6 conditions than for the T8 conditions and higher for the composites than for the base alloys with 4.2 GPa for 2080-T8, 9.3 GPa for 2080-T6, 0.7 GPa for 2080-T8 and 2.6 GPa for 2080-T6. Work hardening rates increased with overaging temperature up to 7.9 GPa for the T8+250 treatment.

The T6 conditions showed generally higher ductilities than the T8 conditions with a tensile elongation of 13.5% for 2080-T6 and of 9.5% for 2080-T8 (Table 1). Ductilities were decreased by the addition of SiC, leading to tensile elongations of 3.1% for 2080/SiC-T6 and 1.4% for 2080/SiC-T8. In the overaged conditions, ductilities increased, up to 4.1% for this condition (Table 1).

FATIGUE PROPERTIES

The composites exhibited superior fatigue resistance compared to that observed for the base alloys in the same heat treatment condition (Figure 4a). 2080/SiC-T8 showed a fatigue strength at 10^7 cycles of 210 MPa, compared to 140 MPa for the base alloy 2080-T8. Similarly, the composite in T6 condition exhibited a fatigue strength of 240 MPa, compared to 170 MPa for the unreinforced base alloy. Despite its lower monotonic strength levels, 2080/SiC-T6 showed longer lifetimes for all stress amplitudes and higher fatigue strength than 2080/SiC-T8 (Figure 4a). 2080-T6 and 2080-T8 had similar lifetimes in the LCF regimen, but 2080-T8 was inferior in the HCF regimen (Figure 4a). For the composites in various T8+overaging heat treatments, the lifetime and fatigue strength decreased with increasing overaging temperature (Figure 4b), with the composite in the T8+250 condition showing a fatigue strength of only 150 MPa.

Fractographic examinations showed that fatigue cracks initiated at the surface or slightly below the surface. In all the 2080 base alloys and in some of the 2080/SiC composites fatigue cracks initiated at surface defects such as inclusions, most of them rich in Si, as exemplified in figure 5a. Also, in the composites large SiC particles or agglomerations of SiC particles acted as crack initiation sites (Figure 5b).

DISCUSSION

MICROSTRUCTURE

The differences in precipitation structure between T8 and T6 conditions and between the T6 base alloy and the T6 composite arise from the nucleation kinetics of S'-precipitates. The semi-coherent S'-precipitates are known to nucleate heterogeneously, particularly at dislocations or grain boundaries [11]. Quenching leads to a greater number of dislocations in the composites than in the base alloys due to residual stresses, which result from the difference in thermal expansion between Al alloy and SiC particles [12]. This leads to a somewhat

Table 1 Tensile Properties of 2080 and 2080/SiC/30_p in T8 and T6 conditions

Condition	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Elongation (%)	Work Hardening Rate (GPa)
2080/SiC-T8	555	600	120	1.4	4.2
2080/SiC-T8+200	425	490	124	2.4	5.8
2080/SiC-T8+225	355	430	124	2.9	7.4
2080/SiC-T8+250	295	375	122	4.1	7.9
2080/SiC-T6	445	560	126	3.1	9.3
2080-T8	525	560	75	9.0	0.7
2080-T6	390	520	74	13.5	2.6

Figure 3 S-N curves of 2080 and 2080/SiC/30_p in T6 and T8 heat treatments

Figure 4 S-N curves of 2080/SiC/30_p in T8 and various overaging treatments

Figure 5 Crack initiation at Si-inclusion in 2080 (a) and large SiC particle in 2080/SiC (b)

higher number of nucleation sites in 2080/SiC-T6 than in 2080-T6 and subsequently to finer precipitates. In both the composite and the unreinforced base alloy in the T6 condition, spatial inhomogeneity of precipitates results from the relatively small number of dislocations present in the matrix (Figure 2c and d). In the T8 condition, the cold rolling step after solutionizing and before aging introduces a high and uniform dislocation density, in both composite and unreinforced base alloy. This results in a large number of nucleation sites and leads to fine and uniformly distributed S'-precipitates both in the base alloy and composite (Figure 2a and b). 2080-T8 and 2080/SiC-T8 exhibited very similar size and spacing of S'-precipitates, thus eliminating indirect strengthening [12] as a composite strengthening mechanism and allowing the unambiguous determination of direct composite strengthening effects. The thermo-mechanical heat treatment as described here was utilized previously to achieve uniformly dispersed precipitates in order to investigate creep properties [13].

TENSILE PROPERTIES

The observed increase in monotonic strength of composites over the base alloys can be attributed to load transfer to the reinforcement, indirect strengthening due to changes in the matrix microstructure and dislocation pile-ups at particle-matrix interfaces, which have been discussed in detail elsewhere [5-8, 15]. In this study, indirect strengthening is largely eliminated in the T8 and T8+OA conditions, as described in the previous section.

The overaging study conducted for T8 heat treatments provides insight into strengthening mechanisms. For the composites subjected to higher aging temperatures, the yield strength dropped as expected as S'-spacing increased. However, the work hardening rate decreased for composites with fine precipitates. Since the S'-precipitates are semi-coherent [11], one explanation might be that the finer precipitates are sheared more easily, thus reducing the amount of work hardening. The coarser and more inhomogeneous S'-precipitates in the T6 conditions would be the least susceptible to shearing. Theoretical models have shown enhanced work hardening rates in composite materials compared to unreinforced alloys due to localized yielding in the composite [7, 12, 14]. This is sometime termed "apparent work hardening", since it does not necessarily result from a change in work hardening mechanism [8]. More detailed investigations of deformation microstructure and slip characteristics are required to further the understanding of the strengthening mechanisms.

FATIGUE PROPERTIES

The process of fatigue failure is affected by a variety of factors, which include monotonic strength, deformation structure, the presence of inclusions and the surface condition. The

role of the SiC particles is twofold in this process: 1) they enhance monotonic and cyclic strength and increase resistance to crack initiation and crack propagation, and 2) they also act as stress raisers which promote crack formation.

In the experiments reported here, considerable improvements in stress controlled fatigue properties are produced by the addition of SiC particles in both heat treatment conditions. A number of studies have reported similar results, although a complete understanding is still lacking [1-10]. The T6 materials showed higher fatigue strengths than the T8 materials (Figure 4a), while they had lower monotonic strengths (Table 1), which is an unexpected observation. The overaging study showed a decrease of fatigue strength (Figure 4b), while the ratio of fatigue strength to yield strength increased slightly from 0.38 for 2080/SiC-T8 to 0.51 for 2080/SiC-T8+250.

At a given level of applied stress, the composite experiences a lower total strain than the unreinforced base alloy. This results from the reduced elastic strain due to the higher modulus of the composite and a reduced plastic strain due to the increased strain hardening rate in the composite [8].

The above considerations concerning monotonic strengthening can also apply to fatigue processes, although the monotonic and cyclic stress-strain response can be vastly different [16]. Presumably, the T8+OA conditions experienced less planar slip than the T8 condition due to the larger size of S' precipitates after overaging. Similarly, shearing of S'-precipitate should be more pronounced in the T8 temper than in the T6 temper. These changes in slip character are reflected in the decreased strain hardening rates observed as precipitate size decreased and in the lower fatigue to yield strength ration with smaller precipitate sizes. Previous investigators have shown that increasing planar slip is detrimental for fatigue resistance of Al-Zn-Cu-Mg alloys [17]. Investigations of Al-Mg-Cu and Al-Mg-Cu-Ag alloys concluded that microstructure and resulting deformation structure have a greater influence on fatigue properties than the level of yield strength [18]. These observations and the results of the tensile tests conducted here suggest the possibility that the T6 conditions experience more homogeneous slip during fatigue compared to the T8 conditions, which would account for the better fatigue properties of the former.

Cyclic stress-strain response is a key experiment in determining whether a material is cyclicly stable. Cyclic stress-strain tests have been conducted in the 2219/TiC_p system, 2124/SiC_p and 6061/SiC_p systems [6, 18]. The tests conducted with 2219/TiC_p composites showed slightly higher hardening rates for the composite than for the unreinforced base alloy at the same initial stress amplitude in fatigue tests and also in tensile tests [6]. The 2124/SiC_p system showed some increase in cyclic hardening when the SiC content was raised from 20 to 30% [18]. These previous results and the increase of monotonic work hardening rate observed in the 2080/SiC-composites here support the notion that the improvements in fatigue behavior produced by the addition of SiC reinforcements are connected to modification of the slip characteristics. Further investigations of stress-strain response are expected to clarify these issues.

An additional factor which must be considered relates to the presence of stress raisers acting as crack initiation sites. Inclusions initiated cracks in all materials investigated; in addition large SiC particles and agglomerations of SiC-particles were factors in the composite materials (Figure 5). To some degree, the observed scatter in lifetime can be correlated to differences in crack initiation sites. When other parameters are unchanged, improved ductility improves the tolerance against stress concentration, thereby delaying crack initiation [16]. The T6 conditions exhibited higher ductilities than the corresponding T8 conditions (Table 1). To some degree, the superior fatigue properties of 2080/SiC-T6 compared to

2080/SiC-T8 and 2080-T6 compared to 2080-T8 can be attributed to the beneficial effects of higher ductility on resistance to fatigue crack initiation.

SUMMARY

- The addition of SiC particles improves both the monotonic and dynamic strength of 2080 Al alloys.
- A thermo-mechanical heat treatment was developed which leads to fine and uniform S'-precipitate size and distribution in both the composite and 2080 Al.
- For 2080/SiC/30_p subjected to this thermo-mechanical processing, the fatigue resistance and tensile strength increased with decreasing precipitate spacing.
- The T6 heat treatment leads to superior fatigue strength, but to lower yield strength levels than the T8 heat treatment.
- The superior fatigue properties of the T6 conditions are attributed to more homogeneous slip characteristics and increased ductility.

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